

Effect of Yoga, Asanas & Pranayama on Quality of Sleep and Concentration (Review Article)

Priti Devi¹ & Arti Yadev²

1. Research scholar, University of Patanjali, Haridwar
2. Assistant Professor, University of Patanjali, Haridwar

Received : 09/05/2023

1st BPR : 26/05/2023

2nd BPR : 07/06/2023

Accepted : 14/06/2023

Abstract

Yoga originated in India thousands of years ago and at present Yoga, Asana and Pranayama which have proved to be an effective method for prevention and management of diseases and improvement of health are being adopted by the people. Yoga (Asana, Pranayama) is the ancient practice has become increasingly popular in today's busy lives. In today's era where modern man is facing health related physical and mental problems at an abnormal rate, Yoga (Asana Pranayama) plays an important role in its solution. The best way to fit ourself. Yoga involves physical poses, and deep breathing. Asanas, Pranayama is a mind and body practice. One can achieve complete control of mind over body by being both physically and mentally fit. Yoga (Asanas, Pranayama) have been practiced in India since ancient times and provides a healthy mind and a sound body. The purpose of this study is to examine the benefits of Asanas, Pranayama on Sleep & Concentration.

Key words: Yoga, Asanas, Pranayama, Quality of Sleep, Concentration.

Yoga is an ancient practice designed to balance all four aspects of a person's physical, mental, emotional and spiritual and to develop human health. It has long been popular in India, "Yoga" means our personal The union of consciousness with the Universal Divine Consciousness in the form of Samadhi, the super-conscious state of knowledge.
- Swami Vivekananda

Asanas: -

Asana is considered a physical state of yoga. It should be performed in three ways: with stability, comfort and joy. When practiced with full awareness and a sense of lightness, the asanas purify the body and mind. Each asana works to energize the body, while we practice the asanas daily, by doing so the blockages and tensions in the physical, mental and emotional body are removed. Originally, eighty-four lakh asanas are mentioned, most of which are named after animals. Observing how animals live in harmony with their environment and with their bodies, the rishis started Observation them so that man could acquire this knowledge also learn to live in harmony with themselves and the environment. Asanas are two type A dynamic and static. The as possible. asanas have a powerful effect on our body and mind in the life, Asanas gently massaging the internal organs, glands, and muscles and relaxing. Dynamic asanas, which are more energetic, speed up the circulation and loosen the muscles and joints, releasing energy and open blocks and removing waste materials from body.

Pranayama (Breath Awareness Prana): -

The origin of Pranayama is from two words "Prana or dimension". Prana a life force that keeps our body alive. 'Prana' refers to our life force and 'Ayama' regulates it. Pranayama, therefore, means to regulate one's life force. Prana travels through the body's many subtle energy glands (called Nadis) and energy centres (called chakras) and is spread all around our body. Creates an aura. It is believed that

whose life force is strong, if the life force is strong and its flow is continuous and stable, then the mind remains happy, calm and enthusiastic. But due to lack of knowledge and not paying attention to the breath, the Nadis of man can cause obstruction in the flow of prana. Such a situation creates apprehension, worries, and fear in the mind. Every trouble first originates in the subtle. Hence any disease first arises in the vital force. When the vital force is low in the body, the person becomes more lethargic and lack of enthusiasm. Toxins then accumulate in these areas and pain, stiffness, and more disease begin. The practice of pranayama starts the flow of prana, which causes toxins to come out and be released. Pranayama practice aims to free the mind from unnecessary thoughts and connect us to joy, love and creativity, integrating and harmonizing body and mind.

Sleep: -

Sleep is natural and you cannot get it by any other means like- with the help of any medicine, equipment, psychiatric counselling and so on. Of course, sleep is as important as our work and our diet. Many people believe that when we sleep, our brain also sleeps, it is very challenging to find the answer. But in reality, the mind never sleeps. Our mind is present in the area around the brain. At the time when we sleep, the thought process of the mind gradually stops. Due to which our daily activities stop, and important messages from the brain also stop and the brain becomes a little relaxed. After that we fall asleep but the brain continues to function to some extent. When we are sleeping, the brain slows down its external work. For this the brain goes through some phases Non-Rapid Eye Movement (NREM) and Rapid Eye (REM) completes its internal work and when it wakes up it is ready with energy and enthusiasm to do a new task.

Source: https://supermemo.guru/wiki/NREM_and_REM_sleep

Source: <https://www.verywellhealth.com/the-four-stages-of-sleep-2795920>

Mental Concentration: -

In today's time mental concentration is a technique to manage our own mind so as to work towards fulfilling the purpose of life which is based on values, according to Swami Vivekananda the difference between the highest and the lowest human being or in other words In successful man and failure is nothing but a mere degree, concentration. For him, the essence of education is concentration of mind and not collection of facts (*Vivekananda, 1963; pp.38-39*)

Source: <https://return2health.com.au/articles/circadian-rhythms>

Circadian rhythm is the 24-hour internal clock in our brain that regulates cycles of alertness and sleepiness by responding to light changes in our environment. Our physiology and behavior are shaped by the Earth's rotation around its axis. (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books>)

There are three aspects of mental concentration

- i) Focus on a particular thing,
- ii) Blocking out all distractions,
- iii) Possessing the power of concentration for extended periods.

Yoga (Asana, Pranayama) effect on Concentration: -

We found some previous study, which reported that yogic practice (Asana Pranayama) improves memory & concentration of school children other researchers found that Transcendental Meditation improved short term memory. Another research studies have shown that yoga and meditation influenced concentration positively. (*KAUTS, et, al.,2012*)

Writer told Six months of yogic practices (asanas, pranayama) brings a feeling of well-being, a reduction in body weight, increased vital capacity, acceleration in endocrinal functions, and improvement in memory. *Udupa et al.* revealed that yoga has the potential to reduce the stress disorder and it helps to achieve physical and metabolic stability. *Sahasi et al.* has demonstrated the effectiveness of yogic techniques in the management of anxiety, stress and reported increased attention/concentration. (*Kauts, et, al.,2009*)

Yoga improve Mental Concentration refers to the technique and power to manage our own mind so that it can work according to the purpose of our lives that is based on values. (Sahoo, et, al.,2021)

Yoga (Asana, Pranayama) effect on Sleep

Sleep disturbances creative mentally disorder physical functionality are common conditions associated with aging. sleep disturbances short term trials of Yoga on sleep have shown beneficial effects: regular Yoga exercises in the daily routine of elderly very effective for sleep disorder. people can help to achieve good sleep quality as well as improve the Life of quality. (Mangesh, et, al.,2021.)

Yoga very effective to be safe and improved sleep quality and Quality of life (QoL) in a group of older adults with insomnia (Altern Ther Health Med. 2014;20(3):37-46.)

It has been reported that older people are more characterized by a decrease in their ability to sleep, which also affects their memory and daytime alertness. Allopathic pharmacological treatment of insomnia in older persons is associated with dangerous side effects. Then it was found that Yoga and Ayurveda used to increase his daily sleep which is very effective for him (Manjunath, et, al.,2005)

Sleep related physical and mental diseases: -

Physical diseases - When we do not get enough sleep, our nature becomes irritable, sad and pessimistic. In addition, not getting enough sleep also affects performance and productivity. Inadequate sleep can impair energy, enthusiasm and concentration. Lack of sleep can lead to obesity, high blood pressure, diabetes, eye disorders, indigestion and piles.

Mental illness - Adequate sleep is very important for emotional stability and for better decision making, once our sleep is disturbed then there is a problem in adjusting with the daily routine which also affects our concentration and we are unable to do our daily activities. Unable to accomplish, eventually used to get irritated on small things the environment around them who remain disturbed in the office as well as at home. When we are mentally exhausted due to sleep disturbance. This process gradually affects our thoughts and can lead to many mental illness like anxiety, stress problem and gradually it will turn into depression.

Conclusion: -

We have found from old studies that daily practice of Yoga - Asanas (physical balance) and Pranayama (mental balance) can increase the power of concentration and calm the mind of a person and relieve the stress caused by the workload of his daily life. Can be reduced, thereby reducing the possibility of causing insomnia. After all, the effect of daily yoga practice proves to be very beneficial in good sleep and concentration.

References:

- Ankerberg J, Weldon J. 'Yoga' in Encyclopedia of New Age Belief. In: Eugene OR, editor. United States: Harvest House Publishers; 1996. p. 593-610.
- Bowker J. The Oxford Dictionary of World Religions. New York: Oxford University Press; 1997. p. 1058-9.
- Bankar, M. A., Chaudhari, S. K., & Chaudhari, K. D. (2013). Impact of long term Yoga practice on sleep quality and quality of life in the elderly. *Journal of Ayurveda and integrative medicine*, 4(1), 28.
- Beddoe, A. E., Lee, K. A., Weiss, S. J., Powell Kennedy, H., & Yang, C. P. P. (2010). Effects of mindful yoga on sleep in pregnant women: a pilot study. *Biological research for nursing*, 11(4), 363-370.
- Banasik, J., Williams, H., Haberman, M., Blank, S. E., & Bendel, R. (2011). Effect of Iyengar yoga practice on fatigue and diurnal salivary cortisol concentration in breast cancer survivors. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners*, 23(3), 135-142.
- Chen, K. M., Chen, M. H., Lin, M. H., Fan, J. T., Lin, H. S., & Li, C. H. (2010). Effects of yoga on sleep quality and depression in elders in assisted living facilities. *Journal of Nursing Research*, 18(1), 53-61.
- Cohen, L., Warneke, C., Fouladi, R. T., Rodriguez, M. A., & Chaoul-Reich, A. (2004). Psychological adjustment and sleep quality in a randomized trial of the effects of a Tibetan yoga intervention in

- patients with lymphoma. *Cancer: Interdisciplinary International Journal of the American Cancer Society*, 100(10), 2253-2260.
- Chopra D. The Seven Spiritual Laws of Yoga. In: Hoboken NJ, editor. United States: John Wiley and Sons; 2004.
 - Damodaran A, Malathi A, Patil N, Shah N, Suryavanshi, Marathe S. Therapeutic potential of yoga practices in modifying cardiovascular risk profile in middle aged men and women. *J Assoc Physicians India* 2002;50:633-9.
 - Fang, R., & Li, X. (2015). A regular yoga intervention for staff nurse sleep quality and work stress: a randomised controlled trial. *Journal of clinical nursing*, 24(23-24), 3374-3379.
 - Gokal R, Shillito L. Positive impact of yoga and pranayam on obesity, hypertension, blood sugar, and cholesterol: A pilot assessment. *J Altern Complement Med* 2007;13:1056-7.
 - Hopkins, J. T., & Hopkins, L. J. (1979). A study of yoga and concentration. *Academic Therapy*, 14(3), 341-345.
 - Halpern, J., Cohen, M., Kennedy, G., Reece, J., Cahan, C., & Baharav, A. (2014). Yoga for improving sleep quality and quality of life for older adults. *Altern Ther Health Med*, 20(3), 37-46.
 - Innes KE, Bourguignon C, Taylor AG. Risk indices associated with the insulin resistance syndrome, cardiovascular disease, and possible protection with yoga: A systematic review. *J Am Board Fam Pract* 2005;18:491-519.
 - Iyengar BKS. Light on Yoga. 2nd ed. New York: Schocken Books; 1976.
 - Khatri D, Mathur KC, Gahlot S, Jain S, Agarwal RP. Effects of yoga and meditation on clinical and biochemical parameters of metabolic syndrome. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* 2007;78:e9-10.
 - Kirkwood G, Rampes H, Tuffrey V, Richardson J, Pilkington K, Ramaratnam S. Yoga for anxiety: A systematic review of the research evidence. *Br J Sports Med* 2005;39:884-91.
 - Kauts, A., & Sharma, N. (2012). Effect of yoga on concentration and memory in relation to stress. *ZENITH international journal of multidisciplinary research*, 2(5), 1-14.
 - Melton GJ. "Yoga" in *New Age Encyclopedia*. Detroit: Gale Research Inc.; 1990. p. 500-9.
 - Manjunath, N. K., & Telles, S. (2005). Influence of Yoga & Ayurveda on self-rated sleep in a geriatric population. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 121(5), 683.
 - McCaffrey R, Ruknui P, Hatthakit U, Kasetsoomboon P. The effects of yoga on hypertensive persons in Thailand. *Holist Nurs Pract* 2005;19:173-80.
 - Madanmohan. Role of Yoga and Ayurveda in Cardiovascular Disease. Available from: <http://www.fac.org.ar/qcvc/llave/c039i/madanmohan.php>. [Last accessed on 2011 Sept 11].
 - Michalsen A, Grossman P, Acil A, Langhorst J, Ludtke R, Esch T, et al. Rapid stress reduction and anxiety reduction among distressed women as a consequence of a three month intensive yoga program. *Med Sci Monit* 2005;11:555-61.
 - Mustian, K. M., Sprod, L. K., Janelins, M., Peppone, L. J., Palesh, O. G., Chandwani, K., ... & Morrow, G. R. (2013). Multicenter, randomized controlled trial of yoga for sleep quality among cancer survivors. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 31(26), 3233.
 - Nanthakumar, C. (2018). The benefits of yoga in children. *Journal of Integrative Medicine*, 16(1), 14-19.
 - Pilkington K, Kirkwood G, Rampes H, Richardson J. Yoga for Depression: The Research Evidence. *J Affect Disord* 2005;89:13-24.
 - PP, S. J., Manik, K. A., & Sudhir, P. K. (2018). Role of yoga in attention, concentration, and memory of medical students. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and pharmacology*, 8(11), 1526-1526.
 - Piña, A. A., Shadiow, J., Fadeyi, A. T., Chavez, A., & Hunter, S. D. (2021). The acute effects of vinyasa flow yoga on vascular function, lipid and glucose concentrations, and mood. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine*, 56, 102585.
 - Pandirajan, S., & Shrivastava, S. R. (2022). Self-reported Smartphone Addiction: Strategies to Counter the Same. *SBV Journal of Basic, Clinical and Applied Health Science*, 5(3), 82-83.
 - Putchavayala, C. K., Singh, D., & Sashidharan, R. K. (2022). A perspective of yoga on smartphone addiction: A narrative review. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 11(6), 2284-2291.

- Raj VA. The Hindu Connection: Roots of New Age. St. Louis: Concordia Publishing House; 1994. p. 62-86.
- Raghuraj P, Ramakrishnan AG, Nagendra HR, Shirley T. Effect of two selected yogic breathing techniques on heart rate variability. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol* 1998;42:467-2.
- Robert AF. Reality Check: Renowned Buddhist scholar Robert Thurman reflects on the Yoga Sutra and how we can know reality for ourselves. *Yoga J*, Mar/Apr 2001. p. 67-71.
- Rao, R. M., Vadiraja, H. S., Nagaratna, R., Gopinath, K. S., Patil, S., Diwakar, R. B., ... & Nagendra, H. R. (2017). Effect of yoga on sleep quality and neuroendocrine immune response in metastatic breast cancer patients. *Indian journal of palliative care*, 23(3), 253..
- Scott B. Exercise or Religious Practice? *The Watchman Expositor* 2001;18:5-13.
- Selvamurthy W, Sridharan K, Ray US, Tiwary RS, Hedge KS, Radhakrishnan U, et al. Anew physiological approach to control essential hypertension. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol* 1998;42:205-13. McCaffrey R, Ruknui P, Hatthakit U, Kasetsoomboon P. The effects of yoga on hypertensive persons in Thailand. *Holist Nurs Pract* 2005;19:173-80.
- Shapiro D, Cook IA, Davydov DM, Ottaviani C, Leuchter AF, Abrams M. Yoga as a complementary treatment of depression: Effects of traits and moods on treatment outcomes. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med* 2007;4:493-502.
- Sinha, V., & Khetmalis, M. S. (2022). Effect of Yoga Nindra on psychological parameters of mood on school level female sports person.
- Telles S, Desiraju T. Oxygen consumption during pranayamic type of very slow-rate breathing. *Indian J Med Res* 1991;94:357-63.
- Telles S, Nagarathna R, Nagendra HR. Breathing through a particular nostril can alter metabolism and autonomic activities. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol* 1994;38:133-7.
- Vivekananda S. *Raja Yoga (34th Impression)*. Advaita Asrama; 2007.
- West J, Otte C, Geher K, Johnson J, Mohr DC. Effects of Hatha yoga and African dance on perceived stress, affect, and salivary cortisol. *Ann Behav Med* 2004;28:114-8.
- Wang, W. L., Chen, K. H., Pan, Y. C., Yang, S. N., & Chan, Y. Y. (2020). The effect of yoga on sleep quality and insomnia in women with sleep problems: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC psychiatry*, 20, 1-19.
- Vivekananda S. *Raja Yoga (34th Impression)*. Advaita Asrama; 2007.

